

Rapid Curing of Composites by Filament Winding Technique

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Outline

- Challenges with current filament winding approaches
- Frontal polymerization
- Frontal curing of composites during filament winding
- Experimental methods
- Understanding the underlying processing science
- Conclusions

Pressure Vessel

Composites are increasingly replacing metals in pressure vessel applications due to their superior strength-to-weight ratio and corrosion resistance

Ando et al., *Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology*, 1974

Blachut et al., *Composite Structures*, 2023

Vasiliev et al., *Composite Pressure Vessels*, 2009

Filament Winding

Filament winding is widely used for manufacturing composite pressure vessels

Ma et al., *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* , 2024

- Fibers are wound on a mandrel using wet or prepreg techniques to tailor mechanical properties
- Conventional curing remains slow and energy-intensive, requiring hours of heating even with optimized processes

Filament Winding with *In-Situ* Curing

Rapid, one-step composite manufacturing enabled by in-situ frontal curing during filament winding

Materials

- Carbon fiber tow
- Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD)
- Second generation grubbs' (GC2)
- Tributyl phosphate (TBP)
- Phenyl cyclohexane (PCH)

Thermal Profile Measurement Setup

- Outer surface temperature measured using a thermal camera
- Inner surface temperature measured using a thermocouple

Dry Fiber Winding

Dry fiber winding is used to study the effect of input power and mandrel rotation on photothermal performance of carbon fiber tows

Higher mandrel speeds improve uniformity but lower the average temperature

Wet Winding

Based on the results of dry fiber winding, two processing conditions are selected for wet winding studies

- Low-power curing starts FP but leaves inner layers uncured
- High-power curing enables full cure but causes uneven through-thickness curing

Wet Winding with Preheating

Preheating during the winding step to increase the initial temperature of the material and its reactivity

Preheating enables more uniform curing and faster initiation of frontal polymerization

Conclusions

- A new approach is developed for rapid, energy-efficient, *in-situ* curing of composites during filament winding using IR-assisted frontal polymerization
- Photothermal-assisted frontal polymerization enables on-mandrel curing of composite parts within minutes
- Varying IR power and mandrel rotation speed affects front propagation dynamics and cure quality
- Preheating during winding enhances front initiation and sustained propagation throughout the composite
- Controlled IR input results in uniform curing, while excessive heating leads to surface defects

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